

Kinetics of Reactions in Heterogeneous Systems. Part II. The Reaction between Benzoyl Chloride and Water.

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In the previous part (p. 719) we have investigated the reaction between carbon disulphide and alkali under different conditions. A considerable part of that reaction takes place in the homogeneous system owing to the appreciable solubility of carbon disulphide in water at the ordinary temperature. The reaction between benzoyl chloride and water is on the other hand a completely heterogeneous reaction, as benzoyl chloride is practically insoluble in water. It has, therefore, to be assumed that the hydrolysis takes place only at the surface of contact and that the resulting substances diffuse away from, and the reacting substances diffuse towards, the surface of contact between the two phases. The equation representing the reaction is as follows :

The velocity of decomposition of benzoyl chloride in ethereal solution by water was investigated by Strauss and Hussey (*Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 2168). Their conclusions are, however, restricted to the comparative activity of the COCl group in various substituted benzoyl chlorides.

EXPERIMENTAL.

As the above equation shows, the acids are produced in the reaction mixture, out of which benzoic acid is very slightly soluble in water at the ordinary temperature. The separation of the solid acid, therefore, introduces a third phase into the reaction mixture and makes the reaction much more complicated. In order to avoid this, the benzoyl chloride was always dissolved in a neutral solvent not soluble in water and capable of dissolving the separated benzoic acid.

After a number of trials we found that a concentration of 0·862N (121·2 g. or 100·00 c.c. benzoyl chloride per litre) was sufficient to keep the benzoic acid completely dissolved throughout the course of the experiment. 10 C.c. of this solution were usually shaken with 50 c.c. of water. We found also that small differences in the nature of the internal surface of the container introduced considerable differences in the amount of the hydrolysis and the same applied also to the shape. The flasks and bottles were, therefore, so chosen that they gave identical results under identical conditions of experimentation. The shaking machine was so constructed that the conical flasks could be fastened on the platform of the same and a uniform to-and-fro movement was obtained. Conical flasks showed themselves to be capable of yielding more uniform and reproducible results.

The benzoyl chloride was allowed to stand for two days over potassium carbonate and then distilled. It was then stored in brown stoppered bottles and the stoppers smeared with pure vaseline.

The method of estimating the amount of reaction was so chosen as to give an idea of the quantity of hydrochloric acid liberated.

In the method employed (Lang and Messinger's method, *Ber.*, 1923, 53, 14, 29) diphenylamine was used as absorption indicator. The indicator was freshly prepared for each titration by mixing 1% solution of diphenylamine in concentrated H_2SO_4 with 1 c.c. of 0·1/N- $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and 10 c.c. of 4-5N H_2SO_4 . The separated water layer was taken in a flask and the indicator added. The mixture was then titrated with the silver nitrate solution. The precipitate, being in an acid solution, is coloured dark green, while the top portion has only a light green colour. The end-point shows a sudden change of colour in the top layer to violet. We found that it was necessary to add one drop of indicator for each 3 c.c. of the decinormal silver nitrate solution required in the titration.

The effect of the change in a number of different factors on the amount of benzoyl chloride hydrolysed was investigated. The results are given below.

Speed of shaking.—As the system is very sensitive to change in speed, this factor was studied in great detail.

TABLE I.

Effect of speed on the extent of reactions.

Volume of water = 50 c.c. Time = 30 min. Amount of 0.8626N soln. of benzoyl chloride used = 10 c.c. Vol. of soln. used for estimating the amount of hydrolysis = 10 c.c.

Benzoyl chloride in monochlorobenzene.		Benzoyl chloride in CS ₂ .			
In 200 c.c. flask at 25°.		In 250 c.c. flask at 29.2°.		In 200 c.c. flask at 29.6°.	
R.P.M.	PhCOCl used up.	R.P.M.	PhCOCl used up.	R.P.M.	PhCOCl used up.
122.7	31.99%	124.0	44.19%	132.2	59.39%
126.5	36.34	129.0	51.75	136.6	61.69
132.16	43.61	137.8	59.30	143.3	69.18
143.46	56.10	144.0	62.22	154.8	76.32
151.0	61.91	158.5	65.12	159.0	79.70
162.66	66.00	161.9	63.96	169.2	77.91
169.03	65.40	173.1	62.50	181.0	76.74
175.66	58.69	187.3	61.05		

It will be seen from Table I, that increase in the speed of shaking is not accompanied by a proportionate increase in the amount of benzoyl chloride decomposed. This is probably due to the fact that a violent to-and-fro motion throws the heavier of the two liquids outwards, towards the walls of the flask and prevents an intimate mixing of the two phases. This view is confirmed by the second experiment where the size of the flask is increased. If a solvent of a density, higher than monochlorobenzene is used, it is also found that the limiting speed, after which a reduction in the extent of reaction sets in, occurs at a lower value. (Compare Table I).

Variation in the total amount of water.—The solvent used was monochlorobenzene and the experiment carried out in a 250 c.c. flask at 25.8°. Other factors are same as before.

TABLE II.

Amount of water.	Total reaction (<i>N</i> /10-NaOH.)	Reaction per unit vol.	PhCOCl used up.
25 c.c.	47.5 c.c.	1.895	55.1%
50	63.0	1.260	73.1
75	70.9	0.945	82.2
100	73.0	0.730	84.6
125	73.1	0.585	84.9
150	73.5	0.490	85.3

We get here results similar to those obtained in the case of the carbon disulphide-alkali system (*loc. cit.*). As the amount of water increases, the reaction does not increase proportionately but diminishes gradually due to the agitation becoming less vigorous on account of the increase in the volume of the liquid and the decrease in the empty space in the containing vessel.

Variation in the amount of benzoyl chloride solution.—The experiment is performed in two stages. The temperature and the speed of shaking differed in the two stages but were constant for one single stage. The reaction was carried out in flat-bottomed flasks of about 300 c.c. capacity with monochlorobenzene as solvent. The benzoyl chloride solution was 0.4313*N*. Other factors were the same as in Table I.

TABLE III.

Temp. = 25.2°. R. P. M. = 132 (average).			Temp. = 25°.0. R. P. N. = 141 (average).		
PhCOCl soln. added.	Total reaction (<i>N</i> /10-AgNO ₃).	PhCOCl used up.	PhCOCl soln. added	Total reaction (<i>N</i> /10-AgNO ₃).	PhCOCl used up.
1.0 c.c.	4.25 c.c.	98.6%	5.0 c.c.	10.25	47.5%
2.0	7.50	87.0	10.0	17.75	41.1
3.0	9.50	73.4	15.0	23.25	35.9
4.0	11.50	60.9	20.0	27.00	31.9
5.0	13.50	60.3	25.0	29.50	27.3
6.0	15.50	60.3			

This system being a perfectly heterogeneous one, the reaction increases proportionately to the amount of benzoyl chloride solution added. When the quantity of benzoyl chloride is very small, it is completely decomposed within the time of the experiment (30 minutes) and hence the slight disproportionality in the initial stages of the reaction.

Effect of the shape of the vessel.—Three flasks with a capacity of about 300 c.c. and of different shapes were selected. Experiments were made with two different speeds with the same flasks. Amounts of reactants, etc., are same as in Table I.

TABLE IV.

Temp. = 25°.

Shape.	R. P. M. = 155.	R. P. M. = 47.
	Total reaction (N/10-NaOH).	Total reaction (N/10-NaOH).
Conical	55.25 c.c.	62.75 c.c.
Flat bottom	52.5	61.5
Round bottom	48.0	69.0

These results indicate that the conical flask is more efficient in causing a more vigorous agitation of the liquids than the other two shapes. It also appears here that with increase of speed, the difference in the amount of reaction diminishes. But no definite conclusion can be drawn, since we have seen that the reaction does not remain proportional to the speed for all speeds. With higher speeds of shaking, we get a decrease in the extent of the reaction.

Use of Different Solvents.

TABLE V,

Vol. of 0.8626 N-benzoyl chloride solution 20 c.c. Amount of water = 50 c.c. Temp. = 24° 8. Time = 30 minutes. Capacity of flask = 250 c.c.

Solvent.	Sp. gravity solvent d_4^{25} .	B. p. of solvent at 760 mm.	Total reaction (N/15AgNO ₃).	PbCOCl decomposed.
CS ₂	1.263	46.2°	55.0 c.c.	63.8%
CHCl ₃	1.480	61.2	35.0	40.6
CCl ₄	1.588	76.74	59.0	68.4
C ₆ H ₅ Cl	1.1042	132.58	45.0	52.2
C ₆ H ₅ Br	1.4886	158.0	37.5	43.5
C ₈ H ₁₉	0.859	138.4	57.5	66.7

The extent of reaction goes on falling in the following order:— Carbon tetrachloride, xylene, carbon disulphide, monochlorobenzene, monobromobenzene, and chloroform, and there is no correlation between the velocity and any single physical property of the solvent.

Velocity Determinations.

TABLE VI.

Amount of H₂O etc., same as in Table I.

Time.	0.8628N-PhCOCl in xylene & H ₂ O at 25°5 (300 c.c. flask, 106 R.P.M.).	In xylene at 25°6 (300 c.c. flask, 107 R.P.M.).	In CHCl ₃ & H ₂ O at 24°8° (250 c.c. flask, 120 R.P.M.).	In CCl ₄ & H ₂ O at 29°4° (138 R.P.M.).	In CS ₂ & H ₂ O at 24°8° (114 R.P.M.).	In Ph Br & water at 29° (138 R.P.M.).	In Ph Cl & H ₂ O at 24°6° (104 R.P.M.).
	0.4313 N-PhCOCl						
	K	K	K	K	K	K	K
15	0.0179	0.0178	0.0066	0.0363	0.0158	0.0229	0.0083
30	0.0178	0.0186	0.0075	0.0363	0.0155	0.0235	0.0081
45	0.0179	0.0179	0.0076	0.0352	0.0156	0.0235	0.0082
60	0.0172	0.0179	0.0071	0.0372	0.0163	0.0232	0.0082
75	0.0185	0.0183	0.0070	—	0.0157	0.0226	0.0084
90	0.0181	0.0170	0.0074	—	0.0166	0.0215	0.0085

In all these reactions the monomolecular formula is applicable within the limits of experimental error.

This means in other words that the reaction is similar to a homogeneous reaction between two substances, one of which is present in large excess. This is an indirect proof of the complete heterogeneous nature of this reaction.

SUMMARY.

1. The reaction in this system is purely a heterogeneous one, benzoyl chloride being insoluble in water. So, unlike the system, carbon disulphide—alkali, this reaction is very sensitive to agitation. The experiments in agitations in this system give peculiar results, and indicate that, not only does the amount of reaction not increase proportionately to the speed of shaking, but that with higher speed of agitation there is actually a decrease in the amount of benzoyl chloride decomposed. Throwing out of the heavier liquid towards the walls of the vessel apparently causes a diminution of the surface of contact. But by using larger vessels for the reaction we can minimise this influence. The specific gravity of the solvents also clearly shows its own influence, in as much as with heavier solvents a greater decomposition is obtained for the same speeds as compared with lighter solvents.

2. When the volume of water is increased without changing the capacity of the vessel, the extent of decomposition per unit volume is decreased, indicating that the agitation is not so vigorous due to the smaller empty space above the liquids. The fall in reaction per unit volume, here is greater than in the homo-heterogeneous system, because the homogeneous part of the reaction (which is not dependent on shaking) is absent. We have a net increase in the total amount of reaction, since the products of decomposition are removed more rapidly in the larger volume of the solvents available.

3. The reaction increases proportionately to the increase in the quantity of the benzoyl chloride solution.

4. A change in shape of the vessels also markedly influences the reaction, conical flasks being more favourable to the decomposition than flat bottomed or round bottomed ones.

5. When different solvents are used for dissolving the benzoyl chloride, we get different results. The reaction goes on diminishing in the following order:—Carbon tetrachloride, xylene, carbon disulphide, monochlorobenzene, monobromobenzene and chloroform. The effect is not apparently due to any one single physical property of the solvent. The determinations of the velocity of reactions in different solvents go to prove that the monomolecular formula is applicable because one of the reactions (*viz.*, water) is present in excess.